

European journal of volunteering and community-based projects Vol.1, No 1; 2024

ISSN: 2724-0592 E-ISSN: 2724-1947

Published by Odiv Casa Arcobaleno

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10655039

POP BALANCE

District of Columbia

Year ended September 30, 2022

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February 1, 2023

Dear Fellow Residents and Friends,

When people across the nation think of Washington, D.C., they often see it as the epicenter of our nation's government—a place of power and politics. While that's certainly a part of our identity, there's so much more to our beloved city than it may seem. We're a community rich in culture, diversity, and opportunity, and we're happy to share the Popular Annual Financial Report (PAFR), made to summarize and simplify the financial information presented in the District's FY 2022 Annual Comprehensive Financial Report (ACFR).

Our city is young, diverse, and full of opportunities. Our strong job market attracts people from around the world, resulting in a rich tapestry of cultures, and experiences. Investment is booming, with \$10.3 billion in development, 29 hotels in the pipeline, and eight opening this year, as 75% of our Capital Assets are in Buildings and Infrastructure. Our parks and cultural sites are bringing millions of dollars in investments, and we're also nearing the completion of phase two of the Wharf, a project that will further enhance our waterfront and bring new opportunities for our residents. Furthermore, increased investment in public health has allowed us to overcome the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic.

First and foremost, I'm delighted to announce that Washington, D.C. has been named the #1 Best City for Black Entrepreneurs highlighting the thriving entrepreneurial spirit that permeates our city, offering a wealth of opportunities for aspiring business owners, particularly within the Black community. But that's not all. The Washington Post has also ranked our city as the #3 Best City for remote work, emphasizing the flexibility and forward-thinking nature of our local job market. Our commitment to innovation and adaptation has made us a hub for remote work, and we continue to invest in that. And thanks to our thriving job market, vibrant nightlife, and the many historic landmarks and outdoor activities, Washington, D.C. has received recognition as one of the best places to live and retire, we rank #39 in Best Places to Live and #82 in Best Places to Retire, by U.S. News & World Report.

We're proud of our achievements, and we're excited to continue building a brighter future.

If you would like more information regarding the District of Columbia Government and its various departments and agencies, please visit the city's website at www.dc.gov. Copies of the financial reports (ACFR and PAFR) can be obtained from: Office of the Chief Financial Officer, Office of Financial Operations and Systems

1100 4th Street, SW, 8th Floor Washington, DC 20024 (202) 442-8200

Website: <https://cfo.dc.gov>

Respectfully submitted,

Demography

- Population: 712,816
- Median Age: 37.5
- Poverty Rate: 15.4%
- Average Annual Salary: \$80,480
- Unemployment Rate: 7.2%
- Median Home Price: \$538,037

Age Distribution

● Under 20 25.5% ● 20-24 6.1% ● 25-34 14.6% ● 35-44 14.6% ● 45-64 26.1% ● 65+ 13.1%

Marital Status Breakdown

● Married 50.9% ● Single 49.1%

👉 About the same number of single people in Washington as national average.

Data sourced from the U.S. Census Bureau's American Community Survey.

Median Earnings by Industry

\$79,279

MEDIAN EARNING MEN ± \$1,258

\$67,414

MEDIAN EARNING WOMEN ± \$1,165

Best in the Nation

for Finances in the “Financial
State of the Cities 2022”

#1

in the US for its park system

#1

city for black entrepreneurs

Population trends

Population

\$64 962 200

Total Personal Income

\$100 017

Per Capita Income

16.10\$

Minimum Wage (per hour)

359 300

Employed residents

5.70%

Unemployment rate

Public education system

2 000+

Average Annual Number of Graduates
Elementary and Secondary schools

760+

Average Annual Number of Graduates
University of the District of Columbia

Statement of Net position

(\$000s)	2022	2021
Current and other assets	11 205 702	11 630 070
Capital assets, net	17 462 480	16 814 048
TOTAL ASSETS	28 668 182	28 444 118
DEFERRED OUTFLOWS OF RESOURCES	1 363 465	110 109
Long-term liabilities	16 771 537	14 829 938
Other liabilities	3 486 272	4 111 604
TOTAL LIABILITIES	20 257 809	18 941 542
DEFERRED INFLOWS OF RESOURCES	1 296 199	2 284 769
Net investments in capital assets	3 187 888	4 007 430
Restricted	2 507 044	2 419 940
Unrestricted	2 782 707	900 546
TOTAL NET POSITION	8 477 639	7 327 916

Ranking and Positions

D.C., has been named one of the “World's Best Cities” for 2023, ranked 17th out of 100 cities worldwide, making one of only five U.S. cities named in the top 20. by international consultant group Resonance’s annual ranking.

#82

Best Places to Retire, by U.S. News & World Report

#39

Best Places to Live, by U.S. News & World Report

#12

Best Places to Travel, by AFAR

#4

Best Cities for Young Professionals, by Niche

Ranking and Positions #2

For the second year in a row, ranked #1 in the United States for its parks system, by the Trust For Public Land

Top U.S. City for ENERGY STAR Certified Buildings, by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency

#3

Best Places for Remote Work, by U.S. News & World Report

#23

Healthiest Cities in the U.S, by Niche

Public Administration Group

The centers of all three branches of the federal government of the United States are in the District: the legislative (Congress), the executive (President), and the judicial branch (Supreme Court). In 1973, Congress passed the District of Columbia Home Rule Act, which provides for a popularly elected Mayor and a 13-member Council. However, Congress maintains authority over the city and may overturn local laws. District residents also elect a nonvoting, at-large Congressional Delegate to the U.S. House of Representatives but the District has no representation in the U.S. Senate.

Legislative	Judiciary	Executive
<p>The District Council is the legislature for the District of Columbia. All races for Council are partisan. Of the 13 Council members, four are elected at-large, as is the Chair, and eight are elected from one of the District's eight wards</p> <p>All legislation enacted, including the annual budget, must be submitted to Congress. There are no exceptions, and any piece of legislation may be amended or overturned</p>	<p>The District has two courts: the DC Court of Appeals, which is the equivalent of state Supreme Courts and Superior Court, which is the trial court for DC.</p> <p>The common thread is that judges for any state are selected by some state action. Judges in the DC Court of Appeals and DC Superior Court are appointed by the President of the United States. DC is the only jurisdiction without the power to appoint its own judges.</p>	<p>The Chief Executive of D.C. is the mayor, who enforce all city law; administer and coordinate city departments, including the appointment of a City Administrator and heads of the departments; set forth policies and agendas, and prepare and submit the DC budget to the Council at the end of each fiscal year. The Mayor signs bills before they become law, but must await Congressional approval.</p>

Councilmembers

Thirteen Members make up the Council: a representative elected from each of the eight wards; and five members, including the Chairman, elected at large

Chairman

Chairman Phil Mendelson

Chairman Pro Tempore

At-Large Councilmember Kenyan R. McDuffie

At-Large

At-Large Councilmember Kenyan R. McDuffie

At-Large Councilmember Anita Bonds

At-Large Councilmember Robert C. White Jr.

At-Large Councilmember Christina Henderson

Councilmembers

Ward Members

Ward 1 Councilmember Brianne K. Nadeau

Ward 2 Councilmember Brooke Pinto

Ward 3 Councilmember Matthew Frumin

Ward 4 Councilmember Janeese Lewis George

Ward 5 Councilmember Zachary Parker

Ward 6 Councilmember Charles Allen

Ward 7 Councilmember Vincent C. Gray

Ward 8 Councilmember Trayon White, Sr.

Committees:

The Council currently has 11 committees that consider legislation related to specific policy matters. Each committee is also responsible for overseeing the local government agencies falling under its purview:

1. Committee of the Whole. Agencies Under this Committee (University of DC., Office of budget and planning, Tax Revision Commission, etc)
2. Committee on Business and Economic Development. Agencies Under this Committee (Board of Accountancy, Department of Insurance, Securities and Banking, etc)
3. Committee on Executive Administration and Labor. Agencies Under this Committee (Board of Ethics and Government Accountability, Department of Human Resources, etc)
4. Committee on Facilities and Family Services. Agencies Under this Committee (Commission on Poverty, Department of Buildings, etc)
5. Committee on Health. Agencies Under this Committee (Board of Medicine, Board of Nursing, etc)
6. Committee on Hospital and Health Equity. Agencies Under this Committee (Commission on Health Disparities, Commission on Health Equity, etc)
7. Committee on Housing. Agencies Under this Committee (Real Estate Commission, Department of Human Services, etc)
8. Committee on the Judiciary and Public Safety. Agencies Under this Committee (District of Columbia National Guard, Criminal Justice Coordinating Council, etc)
9. Committee on Public Works and Operations. Agencies Under this Committee (Commission on Human Rights, Office of Community affairs, etc)
10. Committee on Recreation, Libraries and Youth Affairs. Agencies Under this Committee (Commission on Latino Community Development, Department of Parks and Recreation, etc)
11. Committee on Transportation and the Environment. Agencies Under this Committee (Green Finance Authority, Sustainable Energy Utility Advisory Board, etc)

Central Offices

In addition to the Councilmember and Committee offices, the Council has several central offices responsible for legal and budget support and daily management and operations.

Offices:

- Office of the Secretary
- Office of the General Counsel
- Office of the Budget Director
- Information Technology

Organization Chart

Council of the District of Columbia Organization Chart Council Period 25

Capital assets, net

Revenues

	2022	2021
Charges for services	1 332 752	1 184 058
Operating grants and contributions	6 967 124	7 137 868
Capital grants and contributions	209 696	309 217
Property taxes	2 876 250	3 152 529
Sales and use taxes	1 814 079	1 310 154
Income and franchise taxes	4 102 718	3 486 898
Other taxes	1 282 031	1 104 453
Non-tax revenues	777 332	684 891
TOTAL REVENUES	19 361 982	18 370 068

Revenues distribution

- Charges for services
- Operating grants and contributions
- Capital grants and contributions
- Property taxes
- Sales and use taxes
- Income and franchise taxes
- Other taxes
- Non-tax revenues

Expenses

	2022	2021
Governmental direction and support	1 654 463	1 412 671
Economic development and regulation	858 316	722 913
Public safety and justice	2 242 005	1 880 627
Public education system	3 933 866	3 400 015
Human support services	6 759 631	6 041 025
Operations and infrastructure	1 531 347	1 338 065
Public transportation	447 069	458 346
Interest on long-term debt	367 790	424 627
Office of lottery and gaming	234 895	218 086
Unemployment compensation fund	39 994	1 497 798
Not-for-profit hospital corporation	142 883	150 034
TOTAL EXPENSES	18 212 259	17 544 207

Expenses distribution

- Governmental direction and support
- Economic development and regulation
- Public safety and justice
- Public education system
- Human support services
- Operations and infrastructure
- Public transportation
- Interest on long-term debt
- Office of lottery and gaming
- Unemployment compensation fund
- Not-for-profit hospital corporation

Services realized

Public Education System

Composed of the District of Columbia Public Schools (DCPS), which consists of public elementary and secondary schools, and the University of the District of Columbia, a public urban-focused university.

Housing Finance Agency

The DC Housing Finance Agency (HFA) is an organized financial intermediary and administrator of affordable housing programs and resources for the District of Columbia.

Services realized

Public Safety and Justice

The DC Fire and Emergency Medical Services Department (FEMS) provides fire protection and emergency medical services for the District of Columbia.

The Metropolitan Police Department (MPD) is the primary law enforcement agency for the District.

Department of Public Works

The Department of Public Works (DPW) oversees solid waste and recyclables collection, street cleaning, parking enforcement, and governmental vehicle procurement, maintenance and fueling.

Methodological Notes

The current report reflects 9.6 million enrollments reported as of September 28, 2023, by 54.5 percent of Title IV degree-granting institutions in the U.S. that are participating in the Clearinghouse. Analyses focus on year-over-year percent changes in enrollment between 2021 and 2022, 2022 and 2023, and the two-year cumulative percent change in enrollment from 2021 to 2023, based on the same institutions reporting at the same time across all three years.

NATIONAL COVERAGE OF THE DATA

Clearinghouse data track enrollments nationally and are not limited by institutional and state boundaries. As of fall 2021, institutions actively submitting enrollment data to the Clearinghouse account for 97 percent of all enrollments at Title IV, degree-granting institutions in the U.S. Unlike the Current Term Enrollment Estimates report series, where enrollments are weighted to account for variation in data coverage rates by institution sector and state, the Stay Informed series uses unweighted enrollment counts. This is because the emphasis is on year-over-year percentage changes in enrollment patterns rather than estimating total enrollment numbers.

NEIGHBORHOOD INCOME MEASURE

Income data for each tract are sourced from the U.S. Census Bureau's American Community Survey (ACS) five-year estimates. These are adjusted using Regional Price Parity values from the Bureau of Economic Analysis to account for price level differences by state and metropolitan area.

Methodological Notes

Figure M1. Distribution of 15–17-year-olds by Race/Ethnicity and Neighborhood Income Quintile

Methodological Notes

RACE AND ETHNICITY DATA COVERAGE AND ESTIMATION

Not all institutions report race and ethnicity data to the Clearinghouse. To account for differences in data missing rate, undergraduate and freshman enrollments by race and ethnicity are estimated for the most recent year (fall 2023) based on previous years' patterns of data reporting.

Methodological Notes

URBANICITY (CAMPUS SETTING)

Urbanicity refers to the geographic location of a college categorized on a continuum ranging from urban to rural, as defined by IPEDS. The IPEDS codes incorporate the campus location's population size and distance from an urbanized area, resulting in 12 distinct codes, grouped into the following three categories:

- Urban: Territory inside an urbanized area and inside a principal city
- Suburban: Territory outside a principal city and inside an urbanized area.
- Rural & Town (combined):
 - oTown: Territory inside an urban cluster and outside an urbanized area.
 - oRural: Territory outside of an urban cluster and outside an urbanized area.

Dissemination Plan

Objective: Improve public awareness, engagement, and access to government services and information in the District of Columbia.

Target Audience:

- Residents of the District
- Local businesses and organizations
- Tourists and visitors
- Government employees

Channels:

- Official government website (dc.gov)
- Social media platforms (Twitter, Facebook, Instagram)
- Mobile apps for government services
- Community events and town hall meetings
- Local news outlets and press releases
- Government-sponsored newsletters and email updates
- Government Access Television (e.g., Channel 16)
- Collaboration with community organizations and schools

Dissemination Plan

Objective: Improve public awareness, engagement, and access to government services and information in the District of Columbia.

Content Strategy:

- Timely updates on government services and programs
- Public health alerts and emergency information
- Educational resources on local government
- Promotional content for local events and attractions
- Transparent reporting on government activities and expenditures
- Information on city services (e.g., permits, voting, public transportation)

Engagement Strategies:

- Encourage feedback and questions through social media
- Respond to public inquiries and concerns promptly
- Host public forums and Q&A sessions
- Collaborate with local influencers and community leaders for outreach

Conclusion

This work was completed as part of the Public Management course at the School of Advanced Studies (SAA), University of Turin, under the supervision of Prof. Valerio Brescia. The elements presented in this assignment have been developed in accordance with the guidelines defined by Professors Paolo Biancone, Silvana Secinaro, Valerio Brescia, and Davide Calandra.